

Dhruv Kumar*

Amity Institute of Molecular Medicine and Stem Cell Research, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida (UP), India

Dates: Received: 01 July, 2017; **Accepted:** 19 July, 2017; **Published:** 20 July, 2017

***Corresponding author:** Dhruv Kumar, J3-Block, J3-112, Amity Institute of Molecular Medicine and Stem Cell Research, Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Noida (UP), India, Tel: +91-7082436598; E-mail: dhruvbhu@gmail.com; dkumar13@amity.edu

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Editorial

Cancer is a leading cause of death in men worldwide and the major cause of cancer related death is drug resistance [1,2]. In past few years, scientists have established tumor heterogeneity as a phenomenon of critical importance in the natural history of individual neoplasms and drug resistance [3-5]. The concept of tumor heterogeneity has a major impact on therapeutic approaches [6-9]. Drug resistance creates difficulty in cancer treatment and is directly linked to the tumor progression and poorer prognosis. As tumor heterogeneity is very common in almost all solid tumors, cancer therapy needs to become more personalized, selective, and specific [10-13]. Understanding the mechanisms of tumor heterogeneity and drug resistance will provide sustenance for the future development of personalized cancer medicine.

Tumor heterogeneity (intra-tumoral) has been well-known for past few decades, as it was said that a single tumor consists of many cell subpopulations [6]. The biggest challenge in tumor heterogeneity is to capture all subpopulations of a solid tumor. If tumor cell subpopulation is not proficiently captured, drug-resistant subpopulations will sporadically emerge [14-16]. Some biomedical techniques (eg. Single-Cell Sequencing, Micromanipulation, Laser-Capture Microdissection, Flow Cytometry Using Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting, Whole Genome Amplification, Multi-Regional Sequencing Studies etc.) can be used to detect mutational heterogeneity in solid tumor and to provide personalized therapy [17-19].

In 2012, Gerlinger et al., published an article "Intratumor Heterogeneity and Branched Evolution Revealed by Multiregion Sequencing" in New England Journal of Medicine. In this article, Gerlinger et al. demonstrated that intratumor heterogeneity can contribute to drug resistance which leads to the treatment failure in renal-cell carcinoma [6]. Recently, our group for the first time demonstrated the difference in mutational

Editorial

Role of tumor heterogeneity in drug resistance

heterogeneity varying by subsite in Head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (HNSCC). We demonstrated that Larynx and FOM tumors are more heterogeneous than oral tongue tumor [20,21]. The heterogeneity within tumor specimens may adopt resistance to the standard treatment protocols. These kinds of studies on tumor heterogeneity are relevant to the researchers and clinicians in developing personalized cancer therapy based on identification of specific mutations in tumor samples.

References

1. Fitzmaurice C, Dicker D, Pain A, Hamavid H, Moradi-Lakeh M, et al. (2015) The Global Burden of Cancer 2013. *JAMA Oncol* 1: 505-527. [Link: https://goo.gl/jL4ZUy](https://goo.gl/jL4ZUy).
2. Cherdyntseva NV, Litviakov NV, Denisov EV, Gervas PA, Cherdyntsev ES (2017) Circulating tumor cells in breast cancer: Functional heterogeneity, pathogenetic and clinical aspects. *Exp Oncol* 39: 2-11. [Link: https://goo.gl/xkSLLZ](https://goo.gl/xkSLLZ)
3. Dexter DL, Leith JT (1986) Tumor heterogeneity and drug resistance. *J Clin Oncol* 4: 244-257. [Link: https://goo.gl/j9Fisp](https://goo.gl/j9Fisp)
4. Meacham CE, Morrison SJ (2013) Tumour heterogeneity and cancer cell plasticity. *Nature* 501: 328-337. [Link: https://goo.gl/TRmVZQ](https://goo.gl/TRmVZQ)
5. Fisher R, Pusztai L, Swanton C (2013) Cancer heterogeneity: implications for targeted therapeutics. *Br J Cancer* 108: 479-485. [Link: https://goo.gl/bxAUqW](https://goo.gl/bxAUqW)
6. Gerlinger M, Rowan AJ, Horswell S, Larkin J, Endesfelder D, et al. (2012) Intratumor heterogeneity and branched evolution revealed by multiregion sequencing. *N Engl J Med* 366: 883-892. [Link: https://goo.gl/gXghwm](https://goo.gl/gXghwm)
7. McGranahan N, Swanton C (2015) Biological and therapeutic impact of intratumor heterogeneity in cancer evolution. *Cancer Cell* 27: 15-26. [Link: https://goo.gl/rmLcAY](https://goo.gl/rmLcAY)
8. Singh AK, Arya RK, Maheshwari S, Singh A, Meena S, et al. (2015) Tumor heterogeneity and cancer stem cell paradigm: Updates in concept, controversies and clinical relevance. *Int J Cancer* 136: 1991-2000. [Link: https://goo.gl/Kbm6fd](https://goo.gl/Kbm6fd)
9. Lovly CM, Salama AKS, Salgia R (2016) Tumor Heterogeneity and Therapeutic Resistance. *ASCO Educational B* 585-593. [Link: https://goo.gl/b6nUXi](https://goo.gl/b6nUXi)
10. Nishino M, Jagannathan JP, Krajewski KM, O'Regan K, Hatabu H, et al. (2012) Personalized tumor response assessment in the era of molecular medicine: Cancer-specific and therapy-specific response criteria to complement pitfalls of RECIST. *Am J Roentgenol* 198: 737-745. [Link: https://goo.gl/BCpwUz](https://goo.gl/BCpwUz)

11. Onstenk W, Gratama JW, Foekens JA, Sleijfer S (2013) Towards a personalized breast cancer treatment approach guided by circulating tumor cell (CTC) characteristics. *Cancer Treat Rev* 39: 691-700. [Link: https://goo.gl/5GBz3t](https://goo.gl/5GBz3t)
12. Blankenstein T, Leisegang M, Uckert W, Schreiber H (2015) Targeting cancer-specific mutations by T cell receptor gene therapy. *Curr Opin Immunol* 33: 112–119. [Link: https://goo.gl/UeKZnS](https://goo.gl/UeKZnS)
13. Esposito A, Criscitiello C, Locatelli M, Milano M, Curigliano G (2016) Liquid biopsies for solid tumors: Understanding tumor heterogeneity and real time monitoring of early resistance to targeted therapies. *Pharmacol Ther* 157: 120–124. [Link: https://goo.gl/Q3nrkn](https://goo.gl/Q3nrkn)
14. Marusyk A, Almendro V, Polyak K (2012) Intra-tumour heterogeneity: a looking glass for cancer? *Nat Rev Cancer* 12: 323-334. [Link: https://goo.gl/7UqmBC](https://goo.gl/7UqmBC)
15. Rybinski B, Yun K (2016) Addressing intra-tumoral heterogeneity and therapy resistance. *Oncotarget* 7: 72322-72342. [Link: https://goo.gl/2Q8Z7K](https://goo.gl/2Q8Z7K)
16. McGranahan N, Swanton C (2017) Clonal Heterogeneity and Tumor Evolution: Past, Present, and the Future. *Cell* 168: 613–628. [Link: https://goo.gl/WFuUeB](https://goo.gl/WFuUeB)
17. Navin N, Kendall J, Troge J, Andrews P, Rodgers L, et al. (2011) Tumour evolution inferred by single-cell sequencing. *Nature* 472: 90–94. [Link: https://goo.gl/FmQpTJ](https://goo.gl/FmQpTJ)
18. Patel AP, Tirosh I, Trombetta JJ, Shalek AK, Gillespie SM, et al. (2014) Single-cell RNA-seq highlights intratumoral heterogeneity in primary glioblastoma. *Science* 344: 1396–1401. [Link: https://goo.gl/3RxzDR](https://goo.gl/3RxzDR)
19. Schmidt F, Efferth T (2016) Tumor heterogeneity, single-cell sequencing, and drug resistance. *Pharmaceuticals* 9: 33. [Link: https://goo.gl/uywvMi](https://goo.gl/uywvMi)
20. Ledgerwood LG, Kumar D, Eterovic AK, Wick J, Chen K, et al. (2016) The degree of intratumor mutational heterogeneity varies by primary tumor sub-site. *Oncotarget* 7: 27185-27198. [Link: https://goo.gl/BZoP2t](https://goo.gl/BZoP2t)
21. Nicholas Navin, Jude Kendall, Jennifer Troge, Peter Andrews, Linda Rodgers (2011) Tumor Evolution Inferred by Single Cell Sequencing. *Nature* 472: 90–94. [Link: https://goo.gl/eNSzff](https://goo.gl/eNSzff)